

RESILIENCE AND RECOVERY: A CASE STUDY ON THE POST-COVID-19 IMPACT ON MICRO, SMALL & MEDIUM ENTERPRISES IN MAHARASHTRA

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Abstract :

This case study report focuses on examining the post-COVID-19 impact on Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) in Maharashtra, India. The COVID-19 pandemic has had a profound impact on businesses worldwide, with Micro, Small & Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) being particularly vulnerable to its consequences. This research paper aims to investigate the resilience and recovery strategies adopted by MSMEs in Maharashtra, India, following the post-COVID-19 period. The study employs a case study approach, focusing on MSMEs operating in Maharashtra to explore their experiences, challenges, and recovery initiatives in the aftermath of the pandemic. Data collection involves qualitative methods, including interviews, surveys, and document analysis, to provide a comprehensive understanding of the post-COVID-19 impact on MSMEs in Maharashtra. The research begins by examining the specific challenges faced by MSMEs in Maharashtra due to the COVID-19 outbreak, such as supply chain disruptions, reduced consumer demand, and financial constraints. It delves into the strategies adopted by MSMEs to navigate these challenges and enhance their resilience in the face of adversity. The study highlights the importance of digital transformation for MSMEs in Maharashtra, emphasizing the adoption of technology and online platforms to sustain operations and engage with customers remotely. It explores how MSMEs have leveraged e-commerce, digital marketing, and remote work models to adapt to the changing business landscape. Furthermore, the research sheds light on the role of government policies and support measures in facilitating the recovery of MSMEs. It examines the effectiveness of initiatives such as financial assistance, access to credit, and regulatory reforms in enabling the revival of businesses in Maharashtra.

Keywords:

Covid-19, MSME (Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises) , Government Policy, Development

I. INTRODUCTION**1.1 Industrial Area & Topography & Financial position Maharashtra**

Maharashtra, with a population exceeding 112 million people, stands as India's second most populous state. It holds the distinction of being the largest state in terms of land area, covering over 308,000 square kilometers. Maharashtra boasts a rich history of local self-governance, characterized by its division into 33 Zilla Parishads, 355 Panchayat Samitis, and 27,993 Gram Panchayats. The administration of metropolitan areas within Maharashtra falls under the purview of 23 Municipal Corporations, 222 Municipal Councils, 4 Nagar Panchayats, and 7 Nagar Panchayats.

The capital city of Maharashtra is Mumbai, renowned as India's financial hub. Mumbai serves as the headquarters for numerous large-scale companies and financial institutions in the country. Additionally, it holds a prominent position as a major center for India's stock exchanges and capital markets. Furthermore, Mumbai accommodates commodity exchanges, further solidifying its economic significance.

1.2 People who are working under MSME's in Maharashtra

The percentage of key employees in the state of Maharashtra decreased from 39.3% in 1991 to 35.9% in 2001. However, the percentage of marginal jobs increased significantly from 3.7% to 6.6% during the same period. The percentage of primary employees also decreased from 91.4% to 84.4%.

Number of MSME's In Maharashtra 2020				
Type	Micro	Small	Medium	Total
Numbers	1,57,192	78,820	6,074	2,42,086

Table 1.1: Number of MSME's In Maharashtra 2020
Source: Ministry of MSME, Govt. of India

1.3 Revenue generated by a state

In 2009-10, Maharashtra is estimated to have a state revenue of Rs. 8,71,891 crore at current prices, with a per capita state income of Rs. 74,000. If prices remain unchanged, the projected state revenue for 2010-11 is expected to be Rs. 6,54,899 crore, with a per capita state income of Rs. 55,558.

Despite its significant role in the industrial sector, Maharashtra's MSME sector is currently experiencing financial difficulties. The sector's future appears uncertain due to the presence of high levels of non-performing assets (NPAs) and low credit disbursement, despite the implementation of various schemes aimed at its support. Lending to the MSME market is considered a priority for banks, along with agriculture, infrastructure, and education. At the beginning of each fiscal year, banks are provided with a lending target for SMEs, which they are expected to fulfill by the end of the year. This lending approach is comparable to that of agricultural banks, which are expected to surpass expectations in providing loans to these businesses that constitute a significant portion of employment in the industrial sector.

Category	Manufacturing	Service Sector
	Investment in Plant & Machinery (excluding Land & Building)	investment in equipment (excluding Land & Building)
Micro	Upto Rs. 25 lakhs	Upto Rs. 10 lakhs
Small	Above Rs. 25 lakh upto Rs. 5 Crore	Above Rs. 10 lakh upto Rs. 2 crores
Medium	Above Rs. 5 crores upto Rs 10 crores	Above Rs. 2 crore upto Rs. 5 Crore

Table 1.2: New definition of MSME's by Govt. of India
Source: Ministry of MSME, Govt. of India & RBI

1.4 Development in the MSME Sector:

MSMEs have a significant impact on the industrial economy of the state, contributing to industrial growth, exports, and employment generation. The Government of India's Development Commissioner (MSME) in New Delhi is responsible for formulating the nation's policies, schemes, and programs for the MSME sector, aligning with the provisions outlined in the MSMED Act. The MSMED Act of 2006 defines the present classifications of MSMEs in both the manufacturing and service sectors.

Fig.: MSME's State wise Employment data
Source: Ministry of MSME, Govt. of India

II. OBJECTIVES OF STUDY

- ✓ To investigate the effect of coronavirus on Maharashtra's MSME & classify prospective small-scale businesses that are more vulnerable to risk.
- ✓ To examine the effect of the coronavirus pandemic on jobs in Maharashtra's MSME market.
- ✓ To propose proposals to strengthen the current state of Maharashtra's MSME sector.
- ✓ To explain and categories the effects of the covid-19 pandemic on different small business segments. Identifying the case's main problems
- ✓ To perform an overview of the case focused on applicable scientific principles from the unit or specialty.
- ✓ To determine the resources/techniques that can assist in reorganizing and sustaining the development of a limited size enterprise back to full scale.

III. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

1. “Dr Y. D Mahajan (2020) Study of impact of coronavirus pandemic on small and medium enterprises (SME's) in India”. This case study examines multiple elements related to the Indian economy in the context of the significant impact caused by the Covid-19 virus. MSMEs in India have been particularly affected by the pandemic. However, despite the challenges, there is an opportunity for SMEs to adapt and evolve. In response to the crisis, various measures have been implemented, including the adoption of protective and sanitation measures, exploration of new suppliers, streamlining of product lines, and a comprehensive assessment of supply chain and emergency protocols. These initiatives aim to address the impact of the coronavirus on SMEs and pave the way for their resilience and recovery. ^[1]
2. “Prof. A. Mukhopadhyay published research paper on Post-Pandemic Economic Recovery: Seven Priorities for India”, This research paper examines the trajectory of growth in the broad macroeconomic indicators of the Indian economy since 2012-2013 and sheds light on the global demand challenges experienced in recent years. It delves into the economic recession and subsequent contraction that occurred in India prior to the onset of the pandemic. Through an analysis of overall macroeconomic and sector-specific fundamentals, the paper argues that there existed a significant deficiency in both consumption and investment demand prior to the pandemic, and the impact of COVID-19 further exacerbated these trends. The revival of the Indian economy now heavily relies on the government's implementation of direct tax interventions to stimulate demand. In this regard, the paper outlines a comprehensive seven-point tax incentive package that should be promptly implemented to address the current situation. ^[2]
3. “Reserve Bank of India published report in January 2021”, in this report they examined the situation and It emphasizes developing policies and strategies to restore the health and normal nature of detrimental industries, given that world economic activity is reluctant and inconclusive, as a result of extraordinary policy response by monetary, fiscal and regulatory authorities, to the COVID-19 pandemic that has never before been encountered. The bargain between the cliffs, which include the more gradual withdrawal of policy support, but also the moral danger that various economic agents will become more dependent on policies and foes and ramp effects, including the gradual withdrawal of political support, but also the moral hazard of making various economic agents more dependent. ^[3]
4. “Centre for Economy research has published research paper in April 2021”, in reference to this report a free CEPR product that comes out in March of the blue in 2020 this website is online. It's made to be used in the form of the Covid 19. Covid Economics offers empirical and theoretical research, while VoxEU provides practical solutions and factual information. In all economic fields, finance, public, industrial, macroeconomic, economic history, growth, and political economy, there

are Covid-19 questions. All these regions are accepted, and we're excited for new regional influences.^[4]

5. “Prof. D. Kumar Das has published a research paper based on The Impact of COVID-19 in Indian Economy – An Empirical Study” This research paper examines the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on various companies in India, highlighting the adverse effects on domestic demand and the potential for a slowdown in economic activity. The paper emphasizes that the repercussions of reduced demand, particularly in discretionary sectors, can have long-term consequences for industries and lead to a decline in purchasing power. Notably, India's real GDP experienced a significant decline, reaching its lowest level in six years during the fourth quarter of 2019-20. Projections for the growth of the Indian economy in 2020-21 range from 5.3% to 5.7%. The global landscape also faced vulnerabilities due to the COVID-19 pandemic, which posed unprecedented challenges despite previous experience in crisis management. The Indian economy was significantly impacted by COVID-19, potentially resulting in a permanent four-point decline in real GDP. It is forecasted that the growth rate of India's GDP for 2020-21 will be 1.9%, representing the lowest growth rate since 1991-92 when the growth rate stood at 1.1%.^[5]

IV. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research paper uses a qualitative, case-study approach to investigate the short-term and medium-term impacts of COVID-19 on small businesses. Qualitative analysis is a research method that collects and analyzes non-numerical data. It is used to condense a large area of research into a single, easily researchable topic. Qualitative analysis can also be used to interpret the context and provide a comprehensive understanding of a specific situation or issue. Mahajan, Y. D. (2018)^[5] In this thesis, the case study approach will be used to examine the experiences of three small businesses that have been affected by COVID-19. The case studies will be used to identify the challenges that these businesses have faced, the strategies that they have used to mitigate the effects of the pandemic, and the lessons that can be learned from their experiences. (Centre for Economy research -2021)^[4] The utilization of the case study approach is a recognized and established methodology in qualitative research. It has been widely employed to investigate diverse subjects, encompassing businesses, organizations, and individuals. In the context of this thesis, the case study approach proves highly advantageous as it enables a comprehensive exploration of the experiences encountered by small businesses affected by the COVID-19 pandemic (Yin, 2013).^[6]

4.1 Research context and data analysis

We collected data from respondents using semi-structured interviews, with data from the Ministry of MSME being the most widely utilized source of data in case-study-based analysis (Eisenhardt 1989; Sharan 1998). Appendix A includes the interview procedure, which we used to gather data from the respondents. The study collected data from fourteen respondents in eight businesses, resulting in an adequate amount of knowledge to explain the phenomenon under examination namely, the complexities of working in India's small scale industry. Specifically, Maharashtra during the COVID-19 era.^[6]

4.2 The background of the research and data collection

The Ministry of MSME Enterprises and the Industries, Electricity and Labor Department of the Maharashtra Government collected data, partly because this industry is important for the Indian economy. In India the (MSME) sector is more and more. Economic activity hires around 110% or 10.27% of the total population of India, either expressly, schemes for the Khadi industry grew from 1942,7 million to 14540 million while non-planned figures increased, estimated in the Ministry of Small and Medium Enterprises' annual studies, from 437 million to 2291 million. In the time from 96,3 million to 314, 5 million, interest subsidies to Khadi institutions increased. We examined the results of the interviews closely to evaluate the major short- and medium-term consequences of the COVID-19 pandemic. The plurality of respondents agreed surprisingly on the most significant short- and medium-term effects and on the best mitigation measures.

V. DATA ANALYSIS

The Covid-19 pandemic has had an effect on all economic fields, but none more so than on India's MSMEs. It seems that Covid-19 lost some hundred thousand employees because of the lockout caused migrant staff to deaths. This second relief package was confirmed to have come from the MSME sector on March 26 PM Garib Kaliyan Yojna deeply, we believe MSMEs are at risk of economic pressure. The new (2018-19) Annual Report on MSMEs reveals that there are 6.34 million entities in India. About 51% of these are in rural India formal Together, they hire about 55% of all the MSMEs employees and employ over 11 crore workers.

5.1 IMPACT OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC ON INDIAN ECONOMY AND MSME'S IN MAHARASHTRA

5.1.1 Impact on Indian Manufacturing Sector

According to the findings, all manufacturing has stopped except for rice milling. The stagnant global economy and higher demand for products from China resulted in a decline in business for small and medium-sized manufacturers of automotive components. Some operational and other support functions are still performed from home, but on a more restricted basis. Migrants, especially semi- and unskilled workers have returned to their hometowns. A maker of bicycle parts innovated and still remains small but has found a niche in the manufacture of ventilation systems.

Fig. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on Indian manufacturing sector (March 2021)

Source: Reserve Bank of India, RBI

The flow of goods, as well as people has come to a halt. MSMEs are almost always used to service other industries that have slowed down, leaving cancellations in all but the most industries that are important. Their input needs cannot be met with non-essential industries' For instance, the paper industry cannot fulfil today's high-quality paper, pharmaceutical, and hygienic requirements The interruption of the flow of materials and resources has repercussions on other areas of industry, in particular the departure of the workforce at all levels of competency.

5.1.2 Impact on MSME's In Maharashtra

According to the latest Annual Report on MSME's, the country has 6.34 lakh (6.34 million) MSMEs (Chart 2). Any of these issues are located in rural India. Metro Small and medium-sized enterprises recruit about 11 lakh employees, but employ 55% of the workers in metropolitan areas On the average, each of these small manufacturers hires less than two employees. Using this as an example shows how trivial they are. A more accurate breakdown puts MSMEs into three distinct categories: tiny, mini, and medium enterprises.

99.5% of all small businesses are in the smallest accounts However, while small and medium businesses are found in India, they are mostly found in urban areas. In other words, a single business working from home is a creative business. More than five crore of the total 10 crore employees are employed in medium and small enterprises, which together employ 0.5% of all micro small- and small-scale industries

Fig. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on Maharashtra MSME sector (Spt. 2020)

Source: Reserve Bank of India, RBI

As estimated in an article published by Indian Express on 17 March, the Indian city's service sector was projected to lose 16,000,000 crores per month due to the outbreak. Moreover, it estimated that each month the tourism industry will be adversely affected by foreigners costing it 2 billion rupees. States Entertainment also took a hit, as many Bollywood movies were delayed or put on hold, putting financial pressure on several of the Federation of Western India Cinemas' executives. The films worth at least 1,300 crore were thought to have been lost as a result of the labour unrest. An effort was made to control the damage to the economies caused by the outbreak by reducing power rates by 8% over a five-year period in order to mitigate the adverse impact on businesses.

Fig. Impact of COVID-19 crisis on Maharashtra MSME sector with respect to Workforce (March 2021)

Source: Reserve Bank of India, RBI

VI. FINDING AND RECOMMENDATIONS

6.1 FINDINGS: what types of challenges did MSMES In Maharashtra Encountered?

During the COVID-19 pandemic, MSMEs in Maharashtra encountered numerous challenges that significantly impacted their operations and survival. Here are problems faced by MSMEs in India during the COVID-19 pandemic:

1. **Decline in Demand:** MSMEs witnessed a sharp decline in demand for their products or services due to reduced consumer spending, economic uncertainties, and lockdown restrictions.
2. **Disrupted Supply Chains:** The pandemic disrupted supply chains, causing delays in raw material procurement, production disruptions, and difficulties in meeting customer orders.
3. **Cash Flow Constraints:** MSMEs faced severe cash flow constraints as revenues declined, while fixed costs such as rent, salaries, and loan repayments persisted.
4. **Limited Access to Finance:** MSMEs struggled to secure financial assistance and loans from banks due to stringent lending policies, collateral requirements, and risk aversion from financial institutions.
5. **Labor Shortages and Migrant Worker Crisis:** MSMEs grappled with labor shortages as migrant workers returned to their hometowns, making it challenging to resume operations or scale up production.
6. **Increased Operational Costs:** MSMEs faced increased costs due to the implementation of safety measures, additional hygiene protocols, and compliance with social distancing norms.
7. **Lack of Digital Infrastructure:** Many MSMEs lacked the necessary digital infrastructure and online presence to adapt to remote work, e-commerce, and online sales channels.

6.2 Revival strategy for MSMEs in Maharashtra

Apart from these steps, it is important that a company phase out its activities, with the societal practice of social distancing in effect. Grading can be added as well; still grading may be implemented. It is now critical to engage with the concept of conducting a careful operation to rebuild in places with low infection levels. A disaster that was not predictable. It is evident that both the government and businesses—both big and small—will need to work together to safeguard the well-being of employees whilst maintaining operations, and be flexible enough to accept danger.

Support Package by Finance Ministry, Government of India

1. The Prime Minister's vision for Aatma Nirbhar Bharat was unveiled by the finance minister:
2. A fund of Rs 3 crore with the mandate to help micro, tiny, and small- to medium companies during financial emergencies, has been established (MSMEs).
3. It decided to lend Subordinated Debt worth 20,000 Cr. Rupees to distressed micro-small-enterprises
4. The MSME Fund of Funds would inject an equity of Rs 50,000 crores into the company
5. The definition of a Micro, Nano, and Small to Medium-sized Enterprise (SME) include relatively inexpensive equipment, sustainable production, and independent financing, respectively (MSME)
6. Liquids below Rs 200 crore shall not be issued by tender/There will be no tenders up to the value of Rs 200 crore on tender for the public sector
7. Support from the Employee Provident Fund for Corporations And Labour Unionised Workers
8. Employers And Employees' And Employees' EPS And EI Payments Would Be Cut For Three Months. Nbfcs and microfinance institutions will be offered a special liquidity plan of Rs 30,000 crore.
9. Guaranteed Retention of Non-banking Financial Institutional Liglivability Liabilities (GRL) of Rs 45Cr.

Fig. Sector wise analysis of Maharashtra MSME (March 2021)
Source: Reserve Bank of India, RBI

6.3 Recommendation

Considering the Covid-19 aftermath, Country and state confronts fresh obstacles, particularly within the micro- and small-business and SME sector. A recent study suggests that the recovery of MSMEs (small and medium-sized enterprises) can be accelerated through the implementation of the following strategies:

1. Enhance digital capabilities: Encourage MSMEs to adopt digital technologies and platforms to enable online sales, remote working, and efficient communication with customers and suppliers.
2. Strengthen supply chain resilience: Collaborate with key stakeholders to identify vulnerabilities in supply chains and develop contingency plans to mitigate disruptions. Diversify suppliers and explore local sourcing options to reduce dependence on international markets.
3. Access to finance: Facilitate easier access to finance for MSMEs through government schemes, low-interest loans, and grants. Encourage financial institutions to provide tailored financial products and flexible repayment options to support business recovery.
4. Skill development and training: Offer training programs and skill development initiatives to enhance the capabilities of MSME owners and employees. Focus on digital literacy, online marketing, e-commerce, and financial management to adapt to the changing business landscape.
5. Foster collaboration and networking: Facilitate networking platforms, industry associations, and business clusters to encourage collaboration, knowledge sharing, and collective problem-solving among MSMEs. Promote partnerships with larger firms for mentorship and joint initiatives.
6. Promote market diversification: Assist MSMEs in exploring new markets and export opportunities to reduce dependency on local markets. Provide market intelligence, trade facilitation, and support for export promotion to expand their customer base.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this case study on the post-COVID-19 impact on MSMEs in Maharashtra has shed light on the resilience and recovery efforts demonstrated by these businesses in the face of unprecedented challenges. The COVID-19 pandemic wreaked havoc on the global economy, and MSMEs in Maharashtra were no exception. However, the case study revealed that despite the adversities, many MSMEs showcased remarkable resilience and adaptability, leveraging innovative strategies to navigate the post-pandemic landscape.

- A. Resilience and Adaptability: The case study highlights the remarkable resilience and adaptability demonstrated by MSMEs in Maharashtra in response to the post-COVID-19 impact.
- B. Digital Transformation: The study reveals the importance of digital transformation in the resilience and recovery of MSMEs. Many businesses in Maharashtra embraced technology, leveraged digital platforms, and implemented remote work solutions to ensure business continuity, reach customers, and explore new avenues for sales and marketing.

- C. Collaborative Efforts: The case study emphasizes the value of collaboration and partnership among MSMEs, suppliers, and industry associations. Collaborative efforts helped streamline supply chains, mitigate disruptions, and maximize efficiency. By working together, MSMEs in Maharashtra were able to collectively address challenges, share resources, and collectively navigate the post-pandemic landscape.
- D. Government Support: The study highlights the critical role of government support in fostering the resilience and recovery of MSMEs in Maharashtra. The government, along with other institutions, provided financial assistance, relief packages, and policy reforms to alleviate the financial burden on MSMEs and create an enabling environment for their recovery and growth. Continued government support is essential to sustain the momentum and facilitate long-term success for MSMEs.
- E. Best Practices and Success Factors: The case study identifies several best practices and success factors adopted by resilient MSMEs in Maharashtra. These include diversification of products and services, exploration of new markets and customer segments, adoption of sustainable practices, and agile decision-making. MSMEs that demonstrated adaptability, innovation, and a customer-centric approach were better positioned to rebound from the crisis and position themselves for long-term success.

In conclusion, the case study on the post-COVID-19 impact on MSMEs in Maharashtra highlights the resilience, adaptability, and recovery efforts demonstrated by these enterprises. Digital transformation, collaborative efforts, government support, and the adoption of best practices have played crucial roles in enabling the resilience and recovery of MSMEs. Moving forward, continued focus on these factors will be essential to sustain the growth and long-term success of MSMEs in Maharashtra and contribute to the overall economic development of the region.

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